

Count Your Chickens – Pattern generation as a matter of counting

Rocco Lorenzo Modugno Marco Buiani Amedeo Bonini

Abstract

In this paper we handle pattern generation with a combinatorial approach by framing permutations as numeric literals. We highlight the advantages and limits of this notation to generate and index patterns. We show that this notation is robust, accessible, and tightly linked to existing mathematics, rendering the method universally available in programming languages. This approach allows the users to group the enumerated elements into consistent sets, enabling efficient creation, classification and analysis of patterns. We demonstrate the versatility of this approach with the Chicken Counter¹, named with a play on the old proverb: “don’t count your chickens before they hatch”. It is a web app for visual, pixel-based-pattern exploration and can be considered as an accessible application of our flexible and extensible method. Our aim is to facilitate the application of a combinatorial approach based on the 18th century works of Sebastien Truchet (1704) and Dominique Doüat (1722) extending it within digital environments, scaling the potential of their method and improving the accessibility for computational exploration and creative practices.

Introduction

Historical Foundation

The pattern generation method that we present is grounded on the works of Sebastien Truchet² and Dominique Doüat³ dated 1704 and 1722 respectively.

The bright intuition of Sebastien Truchet was really simple: to apply a combinatorial study to a tiling module, in order to make its aesthetic potential emerge before starting to compose (fig. 1,2).

We can sum up his approach in four passages: 1. Define the initial modules (fig. 1, Table I). 2. Combine the modules in all possible permutations (Table I). 3. Create an

¹The Chicken Counter 1.0 web app <https://countyourchickens.surge.sh/>

²Sebastien Truchet, Memoire sur les combinaisons. Memoires de l’Academie Royale des sciences, Paris, 1704.

³Dominique Doüat, Méthode pour faire une infinité de desseins différents avec des carreaux mi-partis de deux couleurs par une ligne diagonale : ou observations du Père Dominique Doüat, Religieux Carme de la Province de Toulouse, sur un mémoire inséré dans l’Histoire de l’Académie Royale des Sciences de Paris l’année 1704, présenté par le Révérend Père Sébastien Truchet, religieux du même ordre, Académicien honoraire; Printed by Jacques Quillau, Paris, 1722.

Animation generously contributed by Silvia Governa.

ordered index of the permutations based on their visual appearance (fig. 2 Tables II and III). 4. Generate compositions by selecting permutations from the ordered index (fig. 2, Planches des desseins).

TABLE I.
Des 64. combinaisons de deux Carreaux mi-partis de deux couleurs.

TABLE II.
Réduction des 64 combinaisons à 32. figures qui paroissent combinables.

TABLE III.
Réduction des 32. fig. à 10 seulement, mais différemment situés.

Figure 1: Tables I, II, and III from Truchet’s combinatorial method. Truchet used a graphic method to combine the modules. In Table I* he illustrates all 64 possible combinations of tiles, each oriented differently across four columns. In each column, one tile remains fixed in a specific position, while the second rotates through all possible configurations to show every variation. Truchet’s calculations were producing redundant figures, in the Table II all the doubles are removed and he reduces 64 combinations to 32. In Table III all the remaining figures are reduced to 10 main figures, identified by their visual appearance.*

Dominique Douât improved on Truchet’s approach introducing a new notation and calculation method for pattern generation, this made the manual work faster and more accurate.

First, he associates a letter to every spatial configuration of the square module: A, B, C, D (fig. 3). Then, he combines elements 4 by 4 rather than in groups of 2, allowing the system to scale up better and let the aesthetic potential emerge.

In Douât words:

II. Observation The same tile A, when placed in different positions and viewed from the same side, can be considered as four different tiles: this is clear. We will call tile A the one with the colored corner at the bottom left; tile B, the one with the colored corner at the top left; tile C, the one with

Figure 2: “First and second plates of the designs” of Sebastien Truchet, their composition is later described in the text, referring to the ordered index of the Table III.

Figure 3: Spatial configurations of the square module: A, B, C, D

the colored corner at the top right; and tile D, the one with the colored corner at the bottom right. See (Figure 3, first row)

III. Observation The tiles A, B, C, D, when compared with one another, are opposed in three different ways: diagonally, horizontally, and perpendicularly. The tiles A & C, or C & A, B & D, or D & B, are opposed diagonally, that is, from white to black, or from black to white. The tiles A & D, or D & A, B & C, or C & B, are opposed horizontally, that is, from right to left, or from left to right. The tiles A & B, or B & A, C & D, or D & C, are opposed perpendicularly, that is, from top to bottom, or from bottom to top. It is clear, from the mere aspect of the four tiles figured hereafter. See (Figure 3, second row). *Dominique Doüat, Methode pour faire un'infinité des Desseins [...], Paris, 1722. Freely translated by the authors, see original*⁴

Since the appearance and the reciprocal geometric properties of the modules has already been defined, Doüat's notation made the method more efficient and created a "virtual" environment, where one could calculate combinations or notate pleasing visual compositions simply by writing (fig. 4), without even looking at the actual representation.

(Doüat also defined the rules for the catalogation of the obtained permutations, and some generative rules to compose with his notation.)

The main merit of Dominique Doüat is in understanding the power of notation for pattern generation.

Doüat furthermore calculates the total possible compositions in a given space (fig. 5) and defines some generative rules for the composition of drawings⁵.

$$TotalCount = n^k$$

n : number of modules

k : class of the permutation

To conclude, the main difference between the work of Truchet and Douat is the notation: while the first was permutating tiles with a graphical notation, Douat was doing it tipographically, playing with strings.

Modern and contemporary background

The modular approach has already been recognized as a central strategy in contemporary design practice. As Martin Lorenz has demonstrated, modular composition

⁴Original text: Le même carreau A, étant diversement placé et aperçu d'un même côté, peut être regardé comme quatre différents carreaux: cela est clair. Nous appellerons carreau A celui qui a l'angle coloré en bas à main gauche; carreau B, celui qui a l'angle coloré en haut à main gauche; carreau C, celui qui a l'angle coloré en haut à main droite; et carreau D, celui qui a l'angle coloré en bas à main droite. Voyez la planche première, figure 2.

⁵Douat (1722), pp. 18–19.

<p>8 METHODE POUR FAIRE DCDA DAAA DBAA DBCB DBDC DBBB DCBA DCBC DCDB DCCC DABB DCBC DABD DAAB DCBB DABC DABD DAAC DACC DCAB DACD DBBA DBCC DCBA DCAD DBBC DABA DBAC DBCD DCCA DACA DABC DCBD DCCB DBAB DBCA</p> <p>XII. OBSERVATION. Les carreaux A, B, C, & D, pris un à un, deux à deux, trois à trois, quatre à quatre, &c. repétés, reprennent en tout trois cens quarante permutations: ce qui est démontré. Nous représenterons ces 140 permutations en quatre Tables, avec des carreaux figurés, &c. avec des lettres.</p> <p>PREMIERE TABLE, Contenant quatre permutations. Voyez la première Planchette.</p> <table border="1" style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <tr><td>A</td><td>B</td><td>C</td><td>D</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>2</td><td>3</td><td>4</td></tr> </table> <p>SECONDE TABLE Contenant seize permutations. 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Figure 4: Generation of patterns in the notation space. Pages 8, 19 and 10 of the Book of Dominique Doüat (1722).

<p>16 METHODE POUR FAIRE tant de changements, &c. qu'avec les lettres de l'alphabet l'on peut composer tant de differens mots; il n'est pas impossible avec les deux cens cinquante-six permutations des carreaux A, B, C, D, de faire une infinité de dessins differens.</p> <p>PROBLEME. Fixer le nombre de dessins differens qui peuvent être faits avec les deux cens cinquante-six permutations repétés, &c. prisés une à une, deux à deux, trois à trois, quatre à quatre, cinq à cinq, six à six, sept à sept, huit à huit, neuf à neuf, dix à dix, &c. ainsi de suite jusqu'à deux cens cinquante-six.</p> <p>T A B L E Contenant le nombre des Dessins qui peuvent être faits avec les 136 Permutations prisés dans le sens du Probleme.</p> <p>AVERTISSEMENT. POUR éviter cette multitude de chiffres que je serois obligé d'écrire pour dresser cette Table, j'aurai recours à l'Algebre, qui par le moyen des lettres de l'alphabet, &c. des signes qu'elle employe, fait qu'on s'énonce d'une maniere courte & claire, &c. on exprime par une ou plusieurs lettres un grand nombre. Nous supposons que A est égal au nombre 136. Pour marquer le signe d'égalité, nous userons de cette note =; ainsi pour désigner que le nombre 136 est égal à A, nous écrirons seulement A=136. Pour dénoter la seconde puissance du nombre 136, nous écrirons AA, au lieu de 6736, pour dénoter la troisième puissance; qui devroit être désignée par AAA, nous écrirons seulement A³, pour la quatrième puissance A⁴, &c. ainsi de suite.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">AVEC</p>	<p>UNE INFINITE' DE DESSINS. 17 AVEC 136 PERMUTATIONS</p> <table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> Prisés Une à une Deux à deux Trois à trois Quatre à quatre Cinq à cinq Six à six Sept à sept Huit à huit Neuf à neuf Dix à dix Onze à onze. Douze à douze Treize à treize Quatorze à quatorze Quinze à quinze Seize à seize Dix-sept à dix-sept Dix-huit à dix-huit Dix-neuf à dix-neuf Vingt à vingt Et ainsi de suite jusqu'à la 136^{me} puissance. Cette Table étant ainsi continuée jusqu'au nombre de 136 à 136, pour connoître tout d'un coup le nombre des dessins qui peuvent être faits avec ces permutations; il faut remarquer que AA vaut 236 fois davantage que A, que A³ vaut 236 fois davantage que AA, que A⁴ vaut 236 fois davantage que A³, &c. ainsi de suite chaque nombre suivant, étant 236 fois plus grand que celui qui le précède immédiatement. Or une progression étant donnée, connoissant le premier terme, & la raison qui regne, il est facile de connoître quel qu'autre de ses termes qui soit proposé, &c. la somme de tous les termes. </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> l'on peut faire A=136 AA A³ A⁴ A⁵ A⁶ A⁷ A⁸ A⁹ A¹⁰ A¹¹ A¹² A¹³ A¹⁴ A¹⁵ A¹⁶ A¹⁷ A¹⁸ A¹⁹ A²⁰ Dessins differens.</td> </tr> </table> <p style="text-align: center;">XXI. OBSERVATION. Parmi ce nombre prodigieux de dessins, l'on peut en di-</p>	Prisés Une à une Deux à deux Trois à trois Quatre à quatre Cinq à cinq Six à six Sept à sept Huit à huit Neuf à neuf Dix à dix Onze à onze. Douze à douze Treize à treize Quatorze à quatorze Quinze à quinze Seize à seize Dix-sept à dix-sept Dix-huit à dix-huit Dix-neuf à dix-neuf Vingt à vingt Et ainsi de suite jusqu'à la 136 ^{me} puissance. Cette Table étant ainsi continuée jusqu'au nombre de 136 à 136, pour connoître tout d'un coup le nombre des dessins qui peuvent être faits avec ces permutations; il faut remarquer que AA vaut 236 fois davantage que A, que A ³ vaut 236 fois davantage que AA, que A ⁴ vaut 236 fois davantage que A ³ , &c. ainsi de suite chaque nombre suivant, étant 236 fois plus grand que celui qui le précède immédiatement. Or une progression étant donnée, connoissant le premier terme, & la raison qui regne, il est facile de connoître quel qu'autre de ses termes qui soit proposé, &c. la somme de tous les termes.	l'on peut faire A=136 AA A ³ A ⁴ A ⁵ A ⁶ A ⁷ A ⁸ A ⁹ A ¹⁰ A ¹¹ A ¹² A ¹³ A ¹⁴ A ¹⁵ A ¹⁶ A ¹⁷ A ¹⁸ A ¹⁹ A ²⁰ Dessins differens.
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Figure 5: Calculation introduced by Doüat in 1722

provides a flexible framework for developing and applying visual systems in today’s context.⁶

La Scuola Open Source has demonstrated that Douat’s notation is particularly effective for modular font design.⁷ In several workshops, participants used GTL - Generatore Tipografico di Libertà – an open-source software developed by the work cooperative in 2018 – to experiment with the notation and explore how it can support the creation of modular type systems.

In the paper Tiling through Typography⁸, it is demonstrated that Douat’s textual notation can be easily implemented in digital environments. When the modules are encoded as glyphs in a unicase monospaced font, the compositions can be rendered easily. Historically, such typefaces were engraved for letterpress printing, where they served to construct frames and typographic ornaments. These modular systems found renewed applications in the 20th century, such as letter compositions (fig. 6).

Figure 6: The modules of the Typeface Alpha-Blox (American Type Founders, 1944) are inscribed in square movable types. This makes them ideal for combinatorial explorations on a squared grids. Some Architypes such as Albers Architype and Van Doesberg Architype were also designed in a squared grid.

To provide clarity, the same paper introduced a lexicon that we also adopt in this work:

⁶Lorenz, M. (2021). Flexible Visual Systems: A design manual for contemporary visual identities (B. Boyer & D. Marshall, Eds.). Slanted Publishers. ISBN 978-3-948440-30-5

⁷<https://www.lascauolaopensource.xyz/en/archivio/generatore-tipografico-di-liberta>

⁸Modugno, Rocco Lorenzo. 2023. “Tiling through Typography.” In Algorithmic Pattern Salon. Then Try This. <https://doi.org/10.21428/108765d1.7ce0eb8b>.

1. we refer to the initial tiles, along with their possible isometric transformations, as *modules*.
2. The permutations of these modules within any n-class are called *nodes*.
3. Finally, we call *compositions* the resulting tilings obtained by assembling multiple nodes together.

Our counting approach

While Truchet combines modules into nodes through a graphic method, Douat does so through a string-based method. In other words: both approaches rely on the same principle of combining modules, but whereas Truchet *draws* nodes (fig. 7), Douat *writes* nodes (fig. 8).

Figure 7: Sebastien Truchet draws Tilings, in his research he combines the tiles through a graphic approach: the notation and the representation coincide.

AABB

Figure 8: Dominique Douat “writes” Tilings, he notates the four possible configurations of the modules with A, B, C or D.

5

Figure 9: our notation for the same node.

In this paper, we introduce a third approach: we represent modules as digits and combine them into numbers, then produce combinations by enumeration: by *counting nodes* (fig. 9). This shift offers a different mode of representation and reveals new affordances for analysis and application.

Note that in our work we favor the graphical representation of compositions over the textual one. We do so to make these affordances explicit, by adopting a square matrix representation rather than a linear string. This square representation allows for systematic nodes cataloging according to their geometric and chromatic transformations, resulting in a clear classification grounded in visual appearance.

Math foundation

Compositions as permutations with repetition

A composition in the Douat sense is an arrangement of objects where order matters, represented by a string of characters each meaning a module.

A common example of such permutations is **words**: permutations with repetition of symbols from the alphabet. Synonyms for permutations with repetition include

arrangements and *n-tuples* in mathematics, and *strings* in computer science.

Numeric Literals

Numeric literals, the strings representing numbers, can be viewed as permutations with repetition.

Example: the number 10 is represented by the string “10”. Integer numbers from 0 to 99 are all the permutations of 2 symbols from the set of digits $D = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$, indicating all strings from “00” to “99”.

One can see that a decimal string is very similar to the representation of a Douät combination if we view digits as different modules.

$$10 \leftrightarrow BA$$

To allow an arbitrary number of modules and keep this analogy we leap out of decimal notation and generalize to base- n numeric literals. Thus, we can see:

Douät Combinations as base- n numeric literals of class k , where k is the total number of modules and n the number of different modules.

Contextualizing the historical works of Dominique Douät in the setting of math has the obvious reasons of approachability and elegance. Moreover, math has the great advantage of digital portability. Mathematical language and operators are widely implemented in many programming languages.

By viewing Douät strings as numeric literals we facilitate generation and handling of permutations and can exploit the power of efficient math implementation. High generation speed is not only desirable for time saving, it also opens up new affordances to the system, opening the possibility for complete generation of permutation sets: handling all the permutations of a given length at once. We can easily operate with billion of number-only nodes, abstracting away from their string and graphical form. Costly rendering, being it typographic, graphic or musical is performed only as a last, lazy, step.

From Permutations to Counting

We have seen how Douät improves the Truchet approach to pattern generation by implementing a textual notation and operating with patterns as strings.

Once this correspondence is set one can start to think of modules as letters.

a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j, k, l, m, n, o, p, q, r, s, t, u, v, w, x, y, z.

Figure 10: *The latin alphabet letters, “modules” of the English language*

and enumerate all the possible compositions allowed by the generation system:

aa, ab, ac, ad, ae, ...

aaa, aab, aac, aad, ...

Figure 11: *All possible compositions of a fixed length from the English alphabet*

This realization shifts the generation process from manual enumeration to automatic iteration, a far more efficient approach for generating and exploring all possible combinations.

After that, one can see that while all the compositions in a given set are technically valid, only some of them are useful for a given case. This is evident for our language, where many “valid” words are discarded as not useful for many reasons.

an, by, on, up, it, ...
cat, dog, sun, run, hat, ...
book, star, moon, frog, gold, ...
apple, table, chair, house, plant, ...
circle, orange, animal, yellow, summer, ...

Figure 12: *Some useful words in the English language*

This new generate-all-then-filter approach poses new problems of scale for pattern generation, but you will see that we present ways to navigate the newfound complexity by cataloging, ordering and filtering nodes.

Positional notation

While the idea of counting in different bases is second nature to mathematicians, it can seem abstract to the less versed. To ensure clarity for all readers, let’s briefly review how numeric systems generalize Doüat’s combinatorial notation.

In our everyday decimal system (base 10), we use ten digits (0–9). A number with a single digit counts up to 9:

0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9.

two digits count up to 99:

0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9,
10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19,
20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29,
30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39,
40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49,
50, 51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59,
60, 61, 62, 63, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69,
70, 71, 72, 73, 74, 75, 76, 77, 78, 79,
80, 81, 82, 83, 84, 85, 86, 87, 88, 89,
90, 91, 92, 93, 94, 95, 96, 97, 98, 99.

three digits up to 999, and so on – the number of unique representable numbers increases exponentially (to the power of 10) with each additional digit.

Now, if we switch to base 4 and represent using only digits 0–3, a single digit-number counts up to 3;

0, 1, 2, 3.

two digits up to decimal 15:

00, 01, 02, 03,
10, 11, 12, 13,
20, 21, 22, 23,
30, 31, 32, 33.

three digits up to decimal 63:

000, 001, 002, 003, 010, 011, 012, 013,
020, 021, 022, 023, 030, 031, 032, 033,
100, 101, 102, 103, 110, 111, 112, 113,
120, 121, 122, 123, 130, 131, 132, 133,
200, 201, 202, 203, 210, 211, 212, 213,
220, 221, 222, 223, 230, 231, 232, 233,
300, 301, 302, 303, 310, 311, 312, 313,
320, 321, 322, 323, 330, 331, 332, 333.

and four digits up to 255: 0000,, 3333.

In general, with n possible symbols and k digits, we can represent n^k unique combinations.

Doüat’s notation follows this logic exactly: each module is assigned a symbol, and combinations are formed just as numbers are written in a positional numeral system. If we substitute symbols we recover the systematic pattern enumeration found in Doüat’s 1722 book. We adopt the natural mapping from digits to letters in alphabetical order, starting from zero (**fig. 13**).

A	0
B	1
C	2
D	3

Figure 13: *Mapping from modules to digits*

You can find all the nodes presented by Doüat and rewritten in our notation in Appendix C.

Now that we have a clear correspondance, whether we think of modules as letters (where each four-letter “word” is a unique arrangement) or as digits in a number system, the result is the same: we are, at heart, simply counting.

Counting to create a generative system

Following this new theory we can tell that if we imagine a sequence of numbers, we are virtually creating a generative environment. In the following paragraphs we will demonstrate how a simple sequence of increasing numbers can be used to create patterns.

For the sake of simplicity and to streamline our discussion, we will now shift to using a binary (base-2) system in our demonstration.

First of all we will define the parameters of our system, such as the number of modules n and the number of digits k .

Definition of modules To reduce the complexity of our demonstration we are not going to use the “Truchet tile” modules (fig.14), but a white square and a black square as modules, shifting from a four-modules-system to a two-module-system (fig. 15).

Figure 14: Modules used by Sebastien Truchet and Dominique Doüat, often called “Truchet tiles”. $n = 4$.

Figure 15: Modules we are using in our demonstrations. $n = 2$.

Combination of modules in nodes

Defining the number of digits k Now that the number of modules $n = 2$ is fixed, we have to choose the class for our permutation space. With a fast calculation $tot = 2^k$ we can get an idea of how many nodes will be included in our system:

with two digits $k = 2$ we can obtain four nodes $tot = 2^2 = 4$,

00, 01, 10, 11.

with three digits $k = 3$ we can obtain eight nodes $tot = 2^3 = 8$,

000, 001, 010, 011, 100, 101, 110, 111.

with four digits $k = 4$ we can obtain eight nodes $tot = 2^4 = 16$,

0000, 0001, 0010, 0011, 0100, 0101, 0110, 0111,
1000, 1001, 1010, 1011, 1100, 1101, 1110, 1111.

It is clear that some values for k are more useful to us than others: the appropriately-named perfect squares. Integers that can be actually arranged to form a square matrix. In order to obtain a decorative system complex enough we will use sixteen digits $k = 16$, obtaining a total of $tot = 2^{16} = 65.536$ nodes. This class allows us to format the strings of length 16 as 4x4 square matrices.

e.g. number 31828 is binary string 0111110001010100, which can be folded into the following square matrix (using conventional top-down left-right folding):

```
31828 → 0111 1100 0101 0100 → 0 1 1 1
                                     1 1 0 0
                                     0 1 0 1
                                     0 1 0 0
```

Figure 16: Folding of a binary string into a square matrix.

Generating all the nodes

After we have fixed our generation space to two modules $n = 2$ and sixteen digits $k = 16$ we can tell that we will obtain 65.536 nodes. In order to generate them, all we have to do is to count from 0 to 65.535 and convert the base of the numbers from 10 to 2.

We have now obtained 65.536 nodes (binary strings) of 16 digits, composed of 0 and 1.

```
0000000000000000, 0000000000000001,
0000000000000010, 0000000000000011,
0000000000000100, 0000000000000101
... 1111111111111111.
```

These can be folded to square matrices accordingly:

```
0 0 0 0  0 0 0 0  0 0 0 0  ...  1 1 1 1
0 0 0 0  0 0 0 0  0 0 0 0      1 1 1 1
0 0 0 0  0 0 0 0  0 0 0 0      1 1 1 1
0 0 0 0  0 0 0 1  0 0 1 0      1 1 1 1
```

This set includes all the possible nodes that can be created with these two modules with sixteen digits. Every resulting pattern is different from the other by at least one element.

Example The number 2025

1. is converted to the string 0000111111001001,
2. formatted as a square matrix:

3. then represented with modules in a node:

2025 → 0000 1111 1100 1001 →

0	0	0	0
1	1	1	1
1	1	0	0
1	0	0	1

Figure 17: Converting a decimal number to a 4x4 matrix.

Definition of an ordered index of nodes

Identifying binary visual patterns

Following the Truchet approach we now need to index the strings following some criterias. The indexing strictly depends on the purposes of our generative system. If we are going to produce visual patterns, we would want to catalogue nodes based on their visual appearance. In our case 0 and 1 represent a white or black square.

If for instance we consider the nodes obtained as rhythms (0 as silence and 1 as a specific sound), we should index them with different criterias that have more to do with music, rather than visual arts.

In order to demonstrate the improvement of Doüat's notation we keep working on visual patterns, but this time we work with 4x4 square nodes, rather than 16x1 string nodes like Doüat. This will allow us to introduce a new kind of criteria for indexing, based on the symmetries of a square.

Identifying nodes through decimal literals Doüat performs combinatorial calculation and enumerates the results obtained from 1 to n^k . We want to keep naming nodes in decimal notation as it is the most common way to refer to integer numbers. We have also seen that expressing nodes in the natural base, the one that has the selected number of different digits presents many advantages: in the natural base the node Identifier coincides with the node description itself. To uniquely relate decimal representations to base-n strings one can use the base-change transformation, which maintains a one-to-one corispondence without error.

In the case of two modules: - we select $\mathbb{X}=2$ modules and pick a perfect square class, say $k = 16$ - we count the total possible nodes as 2^{16} , from 0 to 65, 535, this decimal number is the node identifier. - we convert to the natural binary base, this is the descriptive string for the node. - we can use this string for visually represent the node in a 4×4 grid.

Limits of using enumeration as an identifier

Using decimal literals as identifiers for compositions poses a problem of long non-descriptive identifier: if we are navigating in a generative system with a large class, it may have so many elements that they have a long name, even if the modules of the system are only two. ::info I.e.

n = 2
k = 36

The node's decimal ID number is:

18.345.642.073.719.551.315

Even if it is shorter than its description in binary notation:

11111110100110001101000001000100010001001000001110110101010011

it results distant from day-to-day numbers. ∴

Another limit consists in having a number of modules bigger than 10 ($n > 10$). In this case the default base-10 identifier of a node would be longer than its "description". It would be paradoxically easier to call a node by its description rather than its identifier.

I.e.

n = 16
k = 8

The node's ID is:

10.268.320

and its representation in hexadecimal notation is:

FAB10

Grouping by node Properties

From the total set of nodes we can select a few with analogue visual properties.

Grouping by Symbol Count Compositions can be indexed, for example, according to the count of total 0 and 1 digits. If 0 is white and 1 is black, this type of indexing corresponds to the average gray value of the composition. #### Indexing based on chromatic opposition This type of indexing leads to a further subdivision: for each composition there exists another in which the 0s and 1s are inverted (**fig. 18**). This allows us to divide the set into two symmetric parts: for any node with $ID = t$ (where t is a decimal number), there exists its chromatic complement $invID = n^k - t - 1$ (where the n is the number of modules, and k is the class of the permutation).

Figure 18: *The node 1658 and its corresponding negative node, 63967.*

Indexing based on the redundancy of square symmetries Each square node possesses 7 geometric symmetries (fig. 19): three rotations (90°, 180°, 270°) and four axial symmetries, corresponding to reflections along the vertical axis, the horizontal axis, and the two diagonals. In addition to these geometric symmetries, in a binary system we consider the inversion of 0 and 1 as a chromatic (or complementary) symmetry. This chromatic inversion is analogous to swapping black and white in the node's configuration, resulting in what we call the complementary node.

Figure 19: 7 geometric symmetries of a square.

As a consequence, each node is associated with a total of 16 related nodes: 8 obtained by applying the 7 geometric symmetries and the original configuration, 8 more by applying the same symmetries to its chromatic complement. This is why nodes are grouped in sets of 16: each set contains a node, all its geometric symmetries, its chromatic complement, and all the symmetries of the complement (fig. 20).

Figure 20: nodes grouped together and their transformations*

Interestingly, not all nodes are unique under these transformations. Some nodes are invariant under certain symmetries; for example, a node that is symmetric with respect to the vertical axis remains unchanged when reflected along that axis (fig. 21).

This redundancy creates a simplification: some of the 16 transformations may yield the same node, reducing the actual number of distinct nodes in the resulting set (fig. 22).

Figure 21: All the symmetries of the node 1638.

Figure 22: All the symmetries of the node 1638 can be reduced to 8 distinct nodes

Indexing nodes according to the type and number of redundant symmetries provides a powerful way to classify them. Nodes with the same redundancy profile share common geometric or chromatic properties, which can be useful for analyzing, selecting specific nodes, or generating patterns within the larger system. An example of this classification can be found in the appendix B.

Higher order compositions

Dominique Doüat described and used some generative rules for creating tilings (“desseins”) by selecting specific permutations from a comprehensive table of all possible combinations of tiles. These rules determine which permutations to choose, how to arrange them, and how to repeat these arrangements. By carefully choosing, positioning, and combining these permutations according to set procedures, Doüat’s approach enables the creation of a wide variety of increasingly complex designs through clear, repeatable steps.

Canons

We refer to this kind of rules with the word “canon”, as a “set of transformations”, a list of operations to execute on the node to produce a larger composition. By working on a square grid we know that combining four adjacent modules in a 2x2 format produces a larger square composition (fig. 23).

Figure 23: A list of four transformations, applied to the input node, and arranged along two rows from top left to bottom right.

```
//Rotations
r90 //90 degree rotation
r180 //180 degree rotation
r270 //270 degree rotation

//Reflections
```

```

mX //reflection on the X axis
mY //reflection on the Y axis
d1 //reflection on the first diagonal
d2 //reflection on the second diagonal

//Chromatic inversion
ne //inversion of "0" and "1"

```

Figure 24: Complete list of transformations with their short name.

In terms of canon notation the order of the sequence always starts from the upper left corner, and follows to the right, then repeats on the new line. This is done to stay coherent to the typographic approach and ensure the same flow of information between nodes, canons, and compositions.

Figure 25: Representation and definition of some basic canons.

```

notation = [n1,n2,n3,n4] =  n1,n2
                           n3,n4

```

```

rep = [n,n,n,n] // Repetition

nRep = [ne,ne,ne,ne] // Negative repetition
altRep = [n,ne,ne,n] // Alternated repetition

refX = [n,n,mX,mX] // Horizontal mirror
refY = [n,mY,n,mY] // Vertical mirror
refD = [n,d2,d2,n] // Diagonal mirror

altRefX = [ne,ne,mX,mX] // Alt. horizontal mirror
altRefY = [n,ne(mY),n,ne(mY)] // Alt. vertical mirror
altRefD = [n,ne(d2),ne(d2),n] // Alt. diagonal mirror

ortho = [n,mY,mX,r180] // Orthogonal
altOrtho = [n,ne(mY),ne(mX),r180] // Alternate orthogonal

rotC = [n,r90,r270,r180] // Concentric rotation
altRotC = [n,ne(r90),ne(r270),ne(r180)] // Neg. conc. rotation

```

Figure 26: *A complete list of the syntax of the canons*

Canon nesting

Founding the system on a power of four principle opens up to many possibilities. By applying a canon to a node, we obtain a composition that is still a perfect square (fig. 28). Therefore, treating the result composition as an input node, we can pass it through a second canon (fig. 29) and repeat the process to get another perfect square. The canon operation exhibits the inherent property of nesting: we can travel through “layers” of canons, increasing the complexity of the resulting composition and its resolution. (fig. 30)

It is important to note that commutative property does not apply to canon nesting: the same canons applied to the node in different order can produce a different composition.

We invite the reader to explore canon nesting in the Chicken Counter tool that we present in Appendix A. It is focused on intuitive exploration of the node symmetries and composition of 3 layers of canons, applied to a manually designed 4x4 node.

Figure 27: *Initial node 2025*

Figure 28: *pattern obtained with diagonalMirror(2025)*

Figure 29: *Pattern obtained with doubleMirror[diagonalMirror(2025)]*

Figure 30: *Pattern obtained with repetition[doubleMirror[diagonalMirror(2025)]]*

Conclusion

This paper has demonstrated how Dominique Doüat’s combinatorial notation can be adapted for computational pattern generation by reframing visual compositions as numeric literals in a positional counting system. By treating Doüat’s combinatorial strings as base- n numbers, we have transformed the manual enumeration process into efficient computational counting, enabling the systematic generation and analysis of all possible pattern combinations within parameter spaces defined by number of different modules and class.

Our approach centers on grouping enumerated elements into coherent sets based on structural properties – particularly symmetry redundancies – which provides a powerful framework for pattern classification and selection. This mathematical foundation honors Doüat’s 18th-century innovations and extends them into contemporary computational practice, revealing new affordances for pattern exploration and generation.

The efficiency gains from treating patterns as numeric literals rather than character strings prove substantial. Operating directly on numbers allows for rapid generation, comparison, and manipulation of entire pattern spaces—transformations that would be computationally expensive when performed on string representations. This numeric approach enables real-time exploration of pattern sets containing tens of thousands of elements, making previously impractical systematic analysis feasible.

Critically, our method reconciles two seemingly conflicting creative approaches. The bottom-up approach begins with mathematical enumeration, building pattern understanding through systematic analysis of all possible combinations and their structural properties, then filtering based on them. Conversely, the top-down approach starts with intuitive exploration, allowing designers to navigate the pattern space guided by aesthetic preference and creative intention. Rather than opposing each other, these approaches prove complementary: systematic enumeration provides the comprehensive foundation that makes intuitive exploration meaningful, while creative navigation reveals which mathematical structures hold visual or functional significance. The filtering and grouping mechanisms serve as the bridge between these approaches, transforming exhaustive mathematical coverage into selective creative discovery.

Further Developments

Free exploration has revealed symmetries emerging from computational analysis rather than traditional geometric classification. Visual analysis of contiguous shapes within patterns and mathematical characterization of node filters require further work. The approach may find application in musical composition and typography, though domain –specific constraints would need consideration.

The companion web application and playground “The Chicken Counter” provides a foundation for further exploration. Taken as a framework, it also opens the possibility of new curated functions to be implemented, leveraging simple interactions for a cascade of effects. Notably, the translation function within the nodes has revealed the

potential to generate “organic” animations, evoking patterns reminiscent of Conway’s Game of Life.⁹.

Appendix A: Pattern playground

With 65,536 chickens scratching in a coop, how can one properly distinguish and move them around?

This paper comes with a companion web app allowing for free exploration of patterns: The Chicken Counter 1.0 is a browser-based interface to navigate the nodes (chickens) and arrange them into more advanced compositions.

It has been designed pursuing the smoothness of interaction. It is meant to be explored intuitively. It works as a playground, we invite you to explore it freely or to start from the selected nodes you encountered in the paper.

The primary parameters of our proposed method have been intentionally fixed for ease of use, and to reduce the complexity of the process to the lowest terms.

The core system of the counter is the decimal number, the unique identifier of each node-chicken (from 0 to 65,535). In this generator we display all the forms a node can take in our system: as a number, as binary strings (graphical or numerical), as binary matrices (graphical or numerical).

Since the number and the strings evade our human ability to graphically evaluate the corresponding node, we arranged the matrices representations at the top of the page. There they serve as the first interactive entry point. Each digit can be clicked and swapped to the opposed binary one, for an extremely intuitive and fast optical-based navigation of the nodes, while live-adjusting the underlying decimal indexing to always point to the correct value.

Whichever node selection route is taken, number or click based, the system responsively updates the others to always be in sync and display the correct decimal and binary representations.

The process so far has established a system to encode, identify and distinguish a precise amount of binary nodes. These nodes, strings of 16 characters, can be represented graphically, by employing a custom typeface that converts 1s to black squares and 0s to white ones.

A note on this choice: despite the semantic representation of 0 as black and 1 as white, we preferred to swap it graphically in order to represent the 1 as “presence of something” and “fullness” with the black square, against the “absence of something” and “emptiness” of the 0.

Our wish is to explore the graphical applications of the modules in a controlled environment, one that can enable us to navigate smoothly through the entire set of possibilities. All of this while maintaining a formal description of each resulting output.

⁹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Conway%27s_Game_of_Life

Lastly, any users wishing to make concrete use of their exploration are welcome to copy the output, and incorporate it into whichever medium of interest they may have. Given the simple binary nature of the output, it may find applications from typography to punchcard for textiles, classic decoration or more advanced computational elaboration.

How to use the Chicken Counter 1.0

When we open the Chicken Counter and at every refresh we visualise a 32x32 composition, obtained through the nesting of three random canons, applied to a random node (chicken).

As a general rule, any red element is interactive, with the addition of the two matrices on the top right - in binary squares and digits.

Figure A1: Screenshot of the Chicken Counter 1.0 - available at countyourchickens.surge.sh

The controls The controls are set to the right side of the window, here we can edit the nodes and the canons of the output composition.

Node Editing The core system of the counter is the number, the unique identifier of each node-chicken. This univocal value is represented five times (fig. A2):

- as 4x4 matrix of binary squares,
- as 4x4 matrix of binary digits,
- as decimal number 2025,

- as string of binary squares
- as string of binary digits 0000011111101001.

Figure A2: The five representations of the chicken.

Both the matrices can have each individual digit clicked to swap it to the other binary value. Additionally, a transformation bar is located under the first matrix (fig. A3). Its different buttons apply the corresponding transformation to the module. From left to right, these are: 1. clockwise rotation, 2. first diagonal symmetry, 3. reflection on the horizontal axis, 4. complementary (negative), 5. reflection across vertical axis, 6. second diagonal symmetry, 7. and counterclockwise rotation.

Figure A3: The seven buttons to apply transformations of the node.

An ulterior tool appears when hovering the square matrix (fig. A4). Four arrows pointing to its different sides, that upon being clicked shift the pattern a column or row up or down, depending on the direction clicked.

Under the node matrices is the Chicken Number, a decimal number input ranging from 0 to 65535, covering all the possible permutations of the class-16 binary module (fig. A5). Once clicked, a new number can be typed in or scrolled to using the up and down arrow keys. By clicking on the round button below, the chicken-number is randomized. On the right the node is represented both as a visual and numeric binary string.

Figure A4: The additional four arrow-buttons to translate the elements within the matrix.

Figure A5: The decimal number, the unique identifier of any single node.

Canon Editing The canons define the arrangement of the node in the larger compositions, they are randomly selected at page loading or by clicking on the title (fig. A6). A maximum nesting of three canons is allowed on the generator. On the right of each canon a black box displays the list of the transformations applied to the node. Canons are activated by default, and can be deactivated by clicking on their letter identifier (the red ❶, ❷ and ❸). By hovering the mouse over the red rectangular buttons, small arrows appears, they can be used to edit the applied canons. Furthermore, clicking on the round red button the canons are randomised.

The output The pattern preview is visible on the left side of the window. The output is read-only, and its content can be copied to the clipboard by clicking the red dot under the bottom-right corner (fig. A7).

It is a string of 1s and 0s separated into lines by carriage returns. You can render this text on any text editor whit this simple font, that displays 1s as black squares ■, and 0s as white ones □. Make sure to give the same value of body size and baseline, so that the squares align exactly.

Textual output example

```
00001010010100000000101001010000
01110110011011100111011001101110
```


Figure A6: The buttons for the canon editing.

Figure A7: The buttons for copying the output.

```

11100110011001111110011001100111
10011100001110011001110000111001
101000000000101101000000000101
01100111111001100110011111100110
01101110011101100110111001110110
11001001100100111100100110010011
11001001100100111100100110010011
01101110011101100110111001110110
01100111111001100110011111100110
101000000000101101000000000101
10011100001110011001110000111001
11100110011001111110011001100111
01110110011011100111011001101110
00001010010100000000101001010000
00001010010100000000101001010000
01110110011011100111011001101110
11100110011001111110011001100111
10011100001110011001110000111001
101000000000101101000000000101
01100111111001100110011111100110
01101110011101100110111001110110
11001001100100111100100110010011
11001001100100111100100110010011
01101110011101100110111001110110
01100111111001100110011111100110
101000000000101101000000000101
10011100001110011001110000111001
11100110011001111110011001100111
01110110011011100111011001101110
00001010010100000000101001010000

```

Figure 38: *Output of the Chicken Counter 1.0, using the node 2025 and applying the diagonal mirror, double mirror, and repetition canons.*

Appendix B: 100 Pixel nodes with dichromatic symmetry in a square matrix of class 16

Our favourite Chickens - Dichromatic Symmetric nodes

Once all possible nodes have been indexed, it becomes easy to isolate those with specific structural properties by applying filtering rules.

Dichromatic symmetry identifies the graphical elements made of only two colors in which the shape of one color and the shape of the chromatic opposite are complementary and identical in shape;

A famous example is the Yin and Yang symbol.

Nodes for which at least one of the fundamental square transformations produces the chromatic inverse are of this kind.

One can reproduce this process as follows: 1. select nodes that are half black, those with the same number of zeroes and ones; 2. apply the 7 square transformations and mark the results; 3. compare each result with the inverse of the original: if one or more matches you got one.

All possible permutations can be filtered to extract compositions with particularly distinctive properties, enabling the abstraction and study of modules that exhibit notable formal or perceptual characteristics.

We further group them in closed sets by the number of unique results after symmetries.

100 Pixel Nodes with dichromatic symmetry

100 Pixel Nodes with dichromatic symmetry in a 4x4 grid

Figure B1: 100 Pixel nodes with

dichromatic symmetry in a square matrix of class 16.

Appendix C: Doüat permutations rewritten with our notation

Doüat permutations rewritten with our notation

Class 10 Numeral String	Class 4 Numeral with Leading 0s	Doüat Notation
0	0000	AAAA
1	0001	AAAB
2	0002	AAAC
3	0003	AAAD
4	0010	AABA
5	0011	AABB
6	0012	AABC
7	0013	AABD
8	0020	AACA
9	0021	AACB
10	0022	AACC
11	0023	AACD
12	0030	AADA
13	0031	AADB
14	0032	AADC
15	0033	AADD
16	0100	ABAA
17	0101	ABAB
18	0102	ABAC
19	0103	ABAD
20	0110	ABBA
21	0111	ABBB
22	0112	ABBC
23	0113	ABBD
24	0120	ABCA
25	0121	ABCB
26	0122	ABCC
27	0123	ABCD
28	0130	ABDA
29	0131	ABDB
30	0132	ABDC
31	0133	ABDD
32	0200	ACAA
33	0201	ACAB
34	0202	ACAC
35	0203	ACAD
36	0210	ACBA

Class 10 Numeral String	Class 4 Numeral with Leading 0s	Doüat Notation
37	0211	ACBB
38	0212	ACBC
39	0213	ACBD
40	0220	ACCA
41	0221	ACCB
42	0222	ACCC
43	0223	ACCD
44	0230	ACDA
45	0231	ACDB
46	0232	ACDC
47	0233	ACDD
48	0300	ADAA
49	0301	ADAB
50	0302	ADAC
51	0303	ADAD
52	0310	ADBA
53	0311	ADBB
54	0312	ADBC
55	0313	ADBD
56	0320	ADCA
57	0321	ADCB
58	0322	ADCC
59	0323	ADCD
60	0330	ADDA
61	0331	ADDB
62	0332	ADDC
63	0333	ADDD
64	1000	BAAA
65	1001	BAAB
66	1002	BAAC
67	1003	BAAD
68	1010	BABA
69	1011	BABB
70	1012	BABC
71	1013	BABD
72	1020	BACA
73	1021	BACB
74	1022	BACC
75	1023	BACD
76	1030	BADA
77	1031	BADB
78	1032	BADC
79	1033	BADD

Class 10 Numeral String	Class 4 Numeral with Leading 0s	Doüat Notation
80	1100	BBAA
81	1101	BBAB
82	1102	BBAC
83	1103	BBAD
84	1110	BBBA
85	1111	BBBB
86	1112	BBBC
87	1113	BBBD
88	1120	BBCA
89	1121	BBCB
90	1122	BBCC
91	1123	BBCD
92	1130	BBDA
93	1131	BBDB
94	1132	BBDC
95	1133	BBDD
96	1200	BCAA
97	1201	BCAB
98	1202	BCAC
99	1203	BCAD
100	1210	BCBA
101	1211	BCBB
102	1212	BCBC
103	1213	BCBD
104	1220	BCCA
105	1221	BCCB
106	1222	BCCC
107	1223	BCCD
108	1230	BCDA
109	1231	BCDB
110	1232	BCDC
111	1233	BCDD
112	1300	BDAA
113	1301	BDAB
114	1302	BDAC
115	1303	BDAD
116	1310	BDBA
117	1311	BDBB
118	1312	BDBC
119	1313	BDBD
120	1320	BDCA
121	1321	BDCB
122	1322	BDCC

Class 10 Numeral String	Class 4 Numeral with Leading 0s	Doüat Notation
123	1323	BDCD
124	1330	BDDA
125	1331	Bddb
126	1332	BDDC
127	1333	BDDD
128	2000	CAAA
129	2001	CAAB
130	2002	CAAC
131	2003	CAAD
132	2010	CABA
133	2011	CABB
134	2012	CABC
135	2013	CABD
136	2020	CACA
137	2021	CACB
138	2022	CACC
139	2023	CACD
140	2030	CADA
141	2031	CADB
142	2032	CADC
143	2033	CADD
144	2100	CBAA
145	2101	CBAB
146	2102	CBAC
147	2103	CBAD
148	2110	CBBA
149	2111	CBbb
150	2112	CBBC
151	2113	CBBD
152	2120	CBCA
153	2121	CBCB
154	2122	CBCC
155	2123	CBCD
156	2130	CBDA
157	2131	CBDB
158	2132	CBDC
159	2133	CBDD
160	2200	CCAA
161	2201	CCAB
162	2202	CCAC
163	2203	CCAD
164	2210	CCBA
165	2211	CCBB

Class 10 Numeral String	Class 4 Numeral with Leading 0s	Doüat Notation
166	2212	CCBC
167	2213	CCBD
168	2220	CCCA
169	2221	CCCB
170	2222	CCCC
171	2223	CCCD
172	2230	CCDA
173	2231	CCDB
174	2232	CCDC
175	2233	CCDD
176	2300	CDA A
177	2301	CDAB
178	2302	CDAC
179	2303	CDAD
180	2310	CDBA
181	2311	CDBB
182	2312	CDBC
183	2313	CDBD
184	2320	CDCA
185	2321	CDCB
186	2322	CDCC
187	2323	CDCD
188	2330	CDDA
189	2331	Cddb
190	2332	CDDC
191	2333	CDDD
192	3000	DAAA
193	3001	DAAB
194	3002	DAAC
195	3003	DAAD
196	3010	DABA
197	3011	DABB
198	3012	DABC
199	3013	DABD
200	3020	DACA
201	3021	DACB
202	3022	DACC
203	3023	DACD
204	3030	DADA
205	3031	DADB
206	3032	DADC
207	3033	DADD
208	3100	DBAA

Class 10 Numeral String	Class 4 Numeral with Leading 0s	Doüat Notation
209	3101	DBAB
210	3102	DBAC
211	3103	DBAD
212	3110	DBBA
213	3111	DBBB
214	3112	DBBC
215	3113	DBBD
216	3120	DBCA
217	3121	DBCB
218	3122	DBCC
219	3123	DBCD
220	3130	DBDA
221	3131	DBDB
222	3132	DBDC
223	3133	DBDD
224	3200	DCAA
225	3201	DCAB
226	3202	DCAC
227	3203	DCAD
228	3210	DCBA
229	3211	DCBB
230	3212	DCBC
231	3213	DCBD
232	3220	DCCA
233	3221	DCCB
234	3222	DCCC
235	3223	DCCD
236	3230	DCDA
237	3231	DCDB
238	3232	DCDC
239	3233	DCDD
240	3300	DDAA
241	3301	DDAB
242	3302	DDAC
243	3303	DDAD
244	3310	DDBA
245	3311	DDBB
246	3312	DDBC
247	3313	DDBD
248	3320	DDCA
249	3321	DDCB
250	3322	DDCC
251	3323	DDCD

Class 10 Numeral String	Class 4 Numeral with Leading 0s	Doüat Notation
252	3330	DDDA
253	3331	DDDB
254	3332	DDDC
255	3333	DDDD

Figure C1: *Doüat permutations rewritten with our notation.*